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Hydrological Characteristics and Crop Planning of 65e/15 Watershed of Kandhamal District of Odisha, India

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Abstract

This experiment was conducted at Dept.of Soil and Water Conservation and Engineering, CAET, OUAT, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India. It was conducted to estimate the hydrologic parameters of 65E/15 watershed of Kandhamal district under North-eastern ghat zone of Odisha. In this study the various hydrological parameters of 65E/15 watershed of Kandhamal district were found out using the toposheet. To carry out this experiment the contour lines were marked to demarcate the high points and the delineation of the watershed was done with this the streamline was also marked which carry the runoff from the entire catchment area. Various features of hydrological parameters were found out. Simulating these data the runoff volume could be calculated and the possibilities of construction of river valley projects in that area can be obtained. The watershed planning and the cropping pattern of the watershed in the command area has been carried out.

Key words: Hydrological Characteristics, Crop Planning, Watershed

Introduction

The watershed 65E/15 is coming under Kandhamal district of Odisha. It has light textured, well drained upland soils and comes under North Eastern Ghat zone of Odisha. The intermittent dry spell and terminal drought affects the crop productivity in most of the year. About 25% of the rainfall is lost as runoff. Harvesting of the run off water in dams will conserve the run off water as well as minimise the soil loss of the watershed. This dam will increase the cropping intensity of the watershed area as well as increase the profit of the farmers.

Watershed based planning will solve this problem. So hydrological parameters will be helpful for this. Ramser(1927), Ghosh (1959), Chow(1964) Nemec (1973) Subudhi (1985), Subudhi (1995), Strahler (1952) & Chorley et al(1985) expressed different types of relationship between the hydrological parameters. Drainage morphology is defined as a measurement of linear a real and relief characteristics of any drainage basin (Clarke 1966) Drainage morphometry was first initiated by Horton (1932).

Protection, improvement and rehabilitation of watersheds are of critical importance to achieve overall watershed development goals. This can be possible only after collecting existing data, analysing and identifying major watershed problems and considering management possibilities. Keeping in view the watershed, developmental and management work has been performed.

Generally, the stored water in the dam was not utilised according to the irrigation and water requirement of crops in different seasons. Due to the improper planning the farmers grow only one crop instead of two to three crops. So to solve this problem software developed by Hembram & Subudhi (2016) was used to calculate water and irrigation requirement of different crops and for every watershed the determination of cropping pattern to increase the cropping intensity of the farmers of this tribal area. So taking into considerations of above problems following objectives were selected:

- To obtain the different watershed characteristics of watershed.
- To obtain the cropping pattern in the command area.

Materials and Methods

Description of Watershed

This study was carried out at Dept. of Soil and Water Conservation, Engineering, College of Agricultural Engineering and Technology, Odisha University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar, Odisha during 2018. The 65E/15 watershed (Figure 1) is in Kandhamal district of Odisha, situated between the longitude of 84°0'36" to 84°1'22" and latitude 20°38'36" to 20°38' with a geographical area of 0.8787 sq km. The Kandhamal district is under the North eastern ghat zone, with an elevation of 300m to 1100m above mean sea level.

Figure 1. Location Map of 65E/15 Watershed

The geographical area is 7654 sq km and forest area of 3624 sq km. It has a subtropical climate characterized by hot and dry summer, cool and humid monsoon and cold and dry winter. The soil type is red late rite, light textured, porous and acidic. The percentage of irrigation done in Kharif and Rabi is 12 and 4.5% respectively. The monsoon scenario of Phulbani normally starts in the second week of June and its cessation in the second week of October. The total rainfall is 1407.4mm with number of rainy days as 65 (Figure 2). The month of August received the highest rainfall as well as highest rainy days. The outlet of the watershed was first marked and then

Figure 2. Normal Rainfall and Rainy Days at Kandhamal

the concentric contour lines were demarcated which shows the high points, joining all the points the delineation of the watershed was done. Delineation is part of the process known as watershed segmentation, i.e., dividing the watershed into discrete land and channel segments to analyze watershed behaviour. This is performed using the tracing paper from the toposheet. The length of the run was calculated using a thread and area using graph paper.

Geomorphologic Characteristics of Watershed

The quantitative land form analysis is undertaken for the developed watershed in which flowing water and associated mass, gravity movements acting over long periods of time are responsible for the development of surface geometry.

Linear Aspects of Drainage Networks

Stream Order

The stream order represents the degree of stream branching with a watershed. Each length of the stream is designated by its order.

Bifurcation Ratio

The bifurcation ratio is defined as the ratio of the number of streams of any order to the number of streams of the next higher order.

Stream Length

The extent of stream length in a watershed reveals the characteristic size of various components of drainage network and its contributing surface area.

Stream Length Ratio

Stream length ratio (RL) is defined as the average length of the stream of any order for the average length of the streams of the next lower order.

Areal Aspects of Watershed

Total Basin Area

The area A_u of a basin of order u is the total area projected on a horizontal plane contributing the overland flow of the streams of giving order plus all the tributaries of lower order.

Basin Shape

The basin shape is the shape of projected surface on the horizontal plane of basin shape. The basin shape has a significant effect on stream discharge characteristics

The quantitative expression of basin can be characterized by Form factor, circularity ratio, elongation ratio

Form Factor (Rf)

The ratio of basin area to the square of the basin length.

Circulatory Ratio (Rc)

Circulatory ratio is the ratio of the basin area (A_u) to the area of the circle an having equal perimeter as the perimeter of the drainage basin.

Elongation Ratio (Rl)

It is the ratio of the diameter of a circle having the same area as the basin to the maximum basin length

Drainage Density (Dd)

The drainage density is defined as the ratio of the total length of all streams of all orders within a watershed to the total area of the watershed.

Stream Frequency

It is the number of stream segments per unit area of the watershed.

Relief Ratio

It is the ratio of relief (elevation difference between reference points located in the drainage basin) to the horizontal distance on which relief was measured.

The crop water requirement (CWR) and irrigation requirement (IR) of various crops were calculated using a web based software. Relevant crop coefficients (K_c), duration of crops and cropping pattern were used to calculate CWR from ET_o . These coefficients present the relationship between references (ET_o) and crop evapotranspiration (ET_{crop}) or $ET_{crop} = K_c * ET_o$. The covered area of all crops (canopy cover) was collected. The K_c values were taken from the FAO. Crop water and irrigation requirement for major crops grown in three seasons, summer (rice, sugarcane, sunflower and watermelon), kharif (long duration paddy, medium duration paddy, short duration paddy, banana, mango, maize, brinjal and ladies finger) and rabi (green gram, black gram, groundnut, maize, sesame, mustard, tomato, potato, cabbage and cauliflower) of the all agro-climatic zones were calculated. By using the software a farmer can find out the water requirement and the irrigation requirement by giving the crop name according to their season and duration of crop Hembram P. & Subudhi C.R. (2016).

Result and Discussion

The different linear aspects were presented in Table 1. The length of run is 4.8 km and maximum width is 1.3 km The different areal

Table 1. Linear Aspects of Drainage Networks

Sl no.	Parameters	Abbreviation	Values
1	Maximum length	L	1.1 km
2	Maximum width	W	1.3 km
3	Stream length ratio	RL	4.363
4	Stream bifurcation Ratio	Rb	0.5
5	Mean bifurcation ratio	Rbm	1.75
6	Length of run		4.8 km
7	Length of overland flow	Lg	0.0914 km
8	Stream length		8.8km
i	1st order		3km
ii	2nd order	Lu	4km
iii	3rd order		
9	Mean stream length		1.257km
i	1st order		1.5km
ii	2nd order	Lsm	4km
iii	3rd order		

aspects were presented in Table 2. The area of the watershed is 0.8787 sq.km. and shape of the watershed is palm shape. Relief

Table 2. Areal Aspects of 67 E/17 Watersheds

Sl no.	Parameters	Abbreviation	Values
1.	Area	A	0.8787 km ²
2	Shape	-	Palm shaped
3	Drainage density A	Dd	5.466Km ⁻¹
4	Stream frequency A	Fs	1.138km ⁻²
5	Drainage texture A	Dt	0.274km ⁻²
6	Circulatory Ratio A	Rc	0.982
7	Form Factor A	Rf	0.591
8	Elongation Ratio A	Re	0.9
9	Compactness coefficient A	Cc	1.098
10	Length/width ratio	-	0.846

aspects of drainage basin: Relief Ratio: (Rh) =0.072

From the above study, we observed that

- After delineating the watershed the shape of the watershed was found to be palm shaped.
 - The tributaries are of approximately same lengths and meet the mainstream at regular intervals.
 - In these wide catchments the peak flood intensity is high since discharges are likely to be distributed over a short period of time.
 - The tributaries are distributed evenly
 - In this watershed cause of flood is high.
 - All the tributaries are of approximately same sizes.
- The length of the run was found to be 4.8 km which indicates good surface runoff of the study area.
- The drainage density (Dd) was found to be 5.466 Km⁻¹ which is a high value and indicates that the basin is moderately impermeable and also high bifurcation ratio indicates higher Dd. It is affected by permeability, climate, vegetation, length of the stream.
- The lower value of stream, frequency i.e.1.138 km⁻² indicates that there is a no quick removal of surface flow of the runoff in the watershed.
- The form factor (A/Lb²) i.e.0.591 indicates that the watershed is elongated and has a longer duration of flow.
- The circulatory ratio i.e.0.982 indicates that the watershed is close to a circular shape

- As the elongation ratio should be between 0.6 to 1.0 .values close to 1 are typical of regions of high relief, whereas, that from 0.6 to 0.8 are associated with high relief and steep ground slope. This ratio is found out to be 0.9; the watershed is considered to be of flat shaped and has a very high relief.
- The compactness coefficient was found out to be 1.098 which indicates it has a less deviation from the circular nature of watershed and it will have less time of concentration before the peak of flow.
- The Cathment and command area was found out to be – 64.5 ha and 23.37 ha respectively.
- The Cropping area in Kharif-23.3 ha, Rabi= 15.533 ha, Summer= 7.796 ha

So, the cropping pattern was planned as Paddy, Mustard, Tomato in kharif, rabi and summer seasons respectively, according to the amount of rainfall the watershed receives every year and water and irrigation requirement for different crops are shown in Table 3.

Conclusions

- The shape of the watershed is palm shaped. Due to wide catchments the peak flood intensity is high since discharges are likely to be distributed over a short period of time.
- The drainage density (Dd) was found to be 5.466 Km⁻¹ which is a high value and indicates that the basin is moderately impermeable and also high bifurcation ratio indicates higher Dd. It is affected by permeability, climate, vegetation, length of the stream.
- The cropping pattern was planned as Paddy, Mustard, Tomato in kharif, rabi and summer respectively.

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Table 3. Water and Irrigation Requirement for Different Crops in the Watershed Command

Crop	Kharif		Rabi		Summer	
	Irrigation requirement (mm)	Water Requirement (mm)	Irrigation requirement (mm)	Water Requirement (mm)	Irrigation Requirement (mm)	Water Requirement (mm)
Paddy (120days)	444	940	-	-	-	-
Mustard (90 days)	-	-	224	309	-	-
Tomato	-	-	-	-	480	598